

**INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH GROUP
ON CHAROPHYTES**

**8TH CONGRESS
ON EXTANT AND
FOSSIL
CHAROPHYTES**

**MUELLER HALL, ROYAL BOTANIC GARDENS
MELBOURNE, AUSTRALIA**

8 - 11 OCTOBER 2024

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

WEDNESDAY 9 TH OCTOBER			
TIME	PRESENTER	TITLE	Page
9:00	Royal Botanic Gardens of Victoria	WELCOME AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT OF COUNTRY	
9:30	BRZOWSKI, M.	RECOVERY OF THE POPULATION OF <i>LYCHNOTHAMNUS BARBATUS</i> IN THE LIGHT OF CLIMATE CHANGE Brzowski, M., Petechaty, M.	19
10:00	GILMORE, A.L.	STATUS OF THE RARE AND ENDANGERED <i>LYCHNOTHAMNUS BARBATUS</i> IN SOUTHEAST QUEENSLAND Gilmore, A.L., Casanova R.L.A., Casanova, M.T.	26
10:30	MORNING TEA		
11:00	SCHUBERT, H.	DEVELOPING STRATEGIES FOR THE PROTECTION OF TAXA CONSISTING OF INTERCONNECTED SEXUAL AND PARTHENOGENETIC REPRODUCING STRAINS – THE ProParts PROJECT Schubert, H., Arnal A., Bernhardt K.-G., García-Murillo P., Guarino R., Rodrigo M.A., Salemi D., Tremetsberger, K., Troia A., Turner B., Weitzel J.	34
11:30	RODRIGO, M.A.	EVALUATION OF THE SEDIMENT PROPAGULE BANKS OF <i>CHARA CANESCENS</i> ALONG EUROPE Rodrigo M.A., Arnal A., Pérez-Márquez A., Giraldo C.A., García-Murillo P., Bernhardt K.-G., Guarino R., Salemi D., Troia A., Turner B., Weitzel J., Schubert, H.	15
12:00	ARNAL, A	BISEXUAL POPULATIONS OF <i>CHARA CANESCENS</i> IN EUROPE: OOSPORE CHARACTERIZATION Arnal A., Rodrigo M.A., Giraldo C.A., Pérez-Márquez A., García-Murillo P., Bernhardt K.-G., Guarino R., Salemi D., Troia A., Turner B., Weitzel J., Schubert, H.	31
12:30	LUNCH		
2:00	CASANOVA, M.T.	CLARIFYING THE TAXONOMY AND CONSERVATION STATUS OF SOME RARE NEW ZEALAND CHAROPHYTES Casanova, M.T., de Winton, M.D., Casanova A.J.	23
2:30	SCHNEIDER, S.C.	TREASURES IN MURKY WATERS? – THE SEARCH FOR <i>CHARA</i> -eDNA IN WATER SAMPLES Schneider, S.C., Marković, A., Vidaković, D., Ballot, A.	33
3:00	BRZOWSKI, M.,	BIOTIC AND ABIOTIC STRESSORS IMPACTING CHAROPHYTE POPULATIONS IN TEMPERATE HARDWATER LAKES Brzowski, M., Heidbüchel, P., Alirangues, M., Hussner, A., Müller, U., Levertz, C., Mauerberger, R., Hilt, S.	
3:30	AFTERNOON TEA		
4:00	BLINDOW, I.	ARE ARCTIC CHAROPHYTES THREATENED BY CLIMATE CHANGE? Böhm, J., Blindow, I., Gyllenstrand, N., Diewald, W., Schubert, H.	18
4:30	BRZOWSKI, M.	CLIMATE WARMING NEGATIVELY AFFECTS CHAROPHYTES THROUGH SHADING BY PERIPHYTON Brzowski, M., Szymańska, P., Petechaty, M., Petechata, A., Szoszkiewicz, K., Hilt, S.	21

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

THURSDAY 9 TH OCTOBER			
TIME	PRESENTER	TITLE	Page
8:50	CASANOVA, M.T.	WELCOME, HOUSEKEEPING	
9:00	SANJUAN, J.	NEOGENE CHAROPHYTE FLORA FROM YALVAÇ AND ILGIN BASINS (CENTRAL ANATOLIA, TÜRKIYE). BIOSTRATIGRAPHY, PALAEO-ECOLOGY AND PALAEOBIOGEOGRAPHY Demirci, E., Sanjuan, J. , and Tunoğlu, C.	25
9:30	LI, SHA.	RESPONSE OF THE LACUSTRINE FLORA IN EAST ASIA TO GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGES ACROSS THE K/PG BOUNDARY Li, Sha , Sanjuan, J., Wang, Q., Zhang, H., Wan, X., Wang, B.	28
10:00	SANJUAN, J.	THE CHAROPHYTE FLORA FROM THE MIOCENE OF CAN GORDEI (LA BISBAL DEL PENEDÈS, CATALONIA, SPAIN). Albaladejo, O., Sanjuan, J. and Marigó, J.	14
10:40	MORNING TEA		
11:00	SANJUAN, J.	THE MIOCENE CHAROPHYTE FLORA IN EUROPE. STATE OF THE ART Vicente, A., Sanjuan, J.	36
11:30	MARTÍN-CLOSAS, C.	NEW INSIGHTS ABOUT THE LATE CRETACEOUS RADIATION OF THE CHARACEAE Martín-Closas, C. , Torromé, D., Vicente, A., Aurell, M.	29
12:00	SANJUAN, J.	OLIGOCENE-EARLY MIOCENE CHAROPHYTES FROM THE SIVAS BASIN (CENTRAL ANATOLIA, TÜRKIYE). BIOSTRATIGRAPHY AND PALAEOBIOGEOGRAPHY Sanjuan, J. , Demirci, E., Özgen-Erdem, N.	32
12:30	LUNCH		
2:00	GROUP PHOTOGRAPH AND GUIDED TOUR OF THE GARDENS		

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

FRIDAY 11TH OCTOBER			
TIME	PRESENTER	TITLE	Page
8:50	CASANOVA, M.T.	WELCOME AND HOUSEKEEPING	
9:00	CASANOVA, A.J.	DOCUMENTATION OF THE CHARACEAE IN THE PARIS CRYPTOGAMIC HERBARIUM (PC) Casanova, M.T., Casanova A.J. , Marani, G., Le Gall, L.	22
9:30	BISSON, M.A.	AN UNEXPECTED ACTOR IN PROMOTING SALT TOLERANCE IN <i>CHARA</i> Phipps, S, Bisson, MA.	17
10:00	PUCHE, E.	DISENTANGLING THE ROLE OF CHAROPHYTES ON GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS FROM FRESHWATER ECOSYSTEMS: A MULTISCALE EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH Puche, E. , Muñoz-Colmenares, M., Pascual-March, C., García-Aibar, S., Rosińska, A., Sánchez-Carrillo, S., Armengol, J., Rodrigo, M.A.	30
10:30	MORNING TEA		
11:00	HEISE, C.M.	EVIDENCE FOR CO ₂ -CONCENTRATING MECHANISM IN <i>CHARA BRAUNII</i> Heise, C.M. , Heß, D., Walke, P., Voß, M., Schubert, H., Hess, W.R., Hagemann, M.	27
11:30	TORN, K.	THE PRIMARY PRODUCTION OF AUSTRALIAN CHAROPHYTES AND ITS IMPACT ON PH AND DISSOLVED OXYGEN FLUCTUATIONS IN DIFFERENT WATERBODIES. Torn, K. , Paalme, T., Pajusalu, L., Albert, G., Casanova, M.T., Martin, G.	35
12:00	CASANOVA, M.T.	OOSPORES ARE DIFFERENT, BUT ARE THEY THE SAME? Casanova, M.T.	24
12:30	LUNCH		
2:00	POSTER SESSION	Mary Beilby: THE MOLECULAR IDENTITY OF THE CHARACEAN OH ⁻ TRANSPORTER: A CANDIDATE RELATED TO THE SLC4 FAMILY OF ANIMAL pH REGULATORS Jo Wilbraham: A GENOMIC APPROACH TOWARDS RESOLVING THE TAXONOMY AND PHYLOGENETIC RELATIONSHIPS OF HISTORIC STONEWORT (CHAROPHYTA) COLLECTIONS Jo Willbraham: CHAROPHYTES OF GREAT BRITAIN AND IRELAND	16 37 38
2:30	CASANOVA, M.T. HANNA, P.	1) RESULTS OF THE CHAROPHYTE BLITZ AT LAKE FYANS 2) PROPOSAL FOR PUBLICATION OF PROCEEDINGS	
3:00	AFTERNOON TEA		
3:30	AGM and election	Suzi Schneider, Kaire Torn, Emile Nat	
6:30	CONFERENCE DINNER	THE BOTANICAL HOTEL, 169 Domain Rd, SOUTH YARRA	

TREASURES IN MURKY WATERS? – THE SEARCH FOR *CHARA*-eDNA IN WATER SAMPLES

¹Schneider, S.C., ²Marković, A., ²Vidaković, D., ¹Ballot, A.

susi.schneider@niva.no

¹ Norwegian Institute for Water Research – NIVA, Økernveien 94, 0579 Oslo, Norway

² University of Belgrade, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Njegoševa 12, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

Charophytes (Charales) inhabit a wide range of habitats, from oligotrophic, crystal-clear lakes to shallow turbid ponds. They can even be found in small pools within agricultural landscapes, provided the water persists after heavy rainfall. However, locating charophytes in turbid waters presents a challenge when relying on conventional field methods such as snorkeling, SCUBA diving or using a bathyscope from a boat. This is because the limited visibility makes it difficult to observe the lake bottom in such murky conditions. It is, therefore, possible that charophytes in turbid waters are frequently overlooked. In addition, conventional fieldwork and species determination often are time-consuming and expensive, even when the lake water is clear. In the BIOLAWEB project, our objective is to make the detection of charophytes easier and more reliable, by developing methods for detecting Chara-DNA in water samples, so-called eDNA. Here, we present preliminary results from four lakes in Serbia - two freshwater and two saline lakes. In addition to traditional charophyte sampling, water samples were analyzed for eDNA. The work is currently ongoing, and we will present a first comparison between the results from traditional sampling and those based on eDNA analysis.

Acknowledgment: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101079234 (BIOLAWEB project).